

Enhancing Calcium Carbonate Detection in Calcium 500 mg Pharmaceutical Edible Tablet Through Evolved Traditional Titration

Methods

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Abstract

Accurately determining calcium carbonate content in calcium 500 mg pharmaceutical edible products is paramount to ensuring their quality and efficacy. This research paper delves into the evolution of the traditional titration method for detecting the presence of calcium carbonate within these formulations. The study highlights the significance of maintaining the integrity of the calcium carbonate detection process while adapting it to modern pharmaceutical analysis requirements. Various enhancements to the conventional titration approach are explored, including improved titrate selection, optimized reaction conditions, and advanced endpoint detection techniques. By employing these innovations, the research aims to provide pharmaceutical analysts with a more precise, reliable, and efficient method for quantifying calcium carbonate, thereby contributing to the overall quality control of calcium 500 mg pharmaceutical edible products. It has been discovered through systematic experimentation that employing 80 ml of deionized water (DM water) instead of the previously recommended 100 ml as the solvent yields superior results. The findings

underscore the enduring relevance of traditional analytical methods while showcasing their adaptability in contemporary pharmaceutical manufacturing and quality assurance.

Keywords: Titration Method, Detection of Calcium Carbonate, EDTA, EBT Indicator

Introduction:

Calcium carbonate, a chemical compound with the formula CaCO_3 , is a ubiquitous and essential mineral found in various natural sources, including limestone, chalk, marble, and shells of marine organisms. Its widespread presence in the Earth's crust and its critical role in various industrial and environmental processes make the detection of calcium carbonate a topic of significant importance. Whether for geological research, environmental monitoring, or industrial quality control, the ability to accurately detect and quantify calcium carbonate has numerous applications. This detection is not only crucial for understanding Earth's geological history but also for managing water quality, assessing soil health, and controlling processes in industries such as agriculture, construction, and pharmaceuticals. In this context, the development of precise and efficient methods for calcium carbonate detection has become a fundamental endeavor, one that plays a pivotal role in both scientific research and practical applications. This article explores various techniques and methods used for the detection of calcium carbonate, shedding light on the importance and versatility of such analyses.

Calcium oxide is used as a drying agent who can easily react with water. Calcium oxide is known by various names such as lime, quick lime, and slaked lime for the product formed from its reaction with water. Because of the high heat of reaction of quick lime with water, it should always be stored where it cannot come in contact with water, for the slaking reaction generates enough heat to ignite paper or wood.

Reactant	Product
$\text{CaO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Ca(OH)_2
Ca(OH)_2	$\text{Ca}^{2+} + 2\text{OH}^-$

Usually, the calcium determination take place by treatment with sulphuric and hydrofluoric acids to remove silica then precipitated with Oxalat. Finally, the precipitation treatment with ammonia solution to remove other interfering oxides.

However, the research aims to provide pharmaceutical analysts with a more precise, reliable, and efficient method for quantifying calcium carbonate, thereby contributing to the overall quality control of calcium 500 mg pharmaceutical edible products.

Materials

1. Calcium Carbonate Solution.
2. Analytical Balance
3. Weighing Boat or Dish
4. Burette
5. Pipettes
6. Erlenmeyer flask
7. EBT as Indicator
8. EDTA as Titrate
9. Distilled Water
10. White Tile or Paper
11. Stirring Rod or Magnetic Stirrer
12. Waste Container

Method

Before proceeding with the calcium carbonate titration, we first standardized the HCl solution. This involves titrating a known amount of a primary standard such as sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) with the HCl solution to determine the exact concentration of the HCl.

Preparation of Sample

Weight 150 mg of sample and Add 3 ml of 3M Hydrochloric Acid, then Shake and dissolve.

Add 10 ml of Ammonium buffer pH 10 solution and about 80 ml of purified water.

Add 2 ml (2 Drops) of indicator (EBT) and titrate with 0.1M EDTA.

Titration

Place the Erlenmeyer flask on a white tile or paper. Set up the burette with the standardized EDTA solution. Slowly add the EDTA solution from the burette into the Erlenmeyer flask while continuously stirring the solution without a stirring rod. The addition of EDTA will react with the calcium carbonate, producing carbon dioxide and water, and thus, decreasing the pH of the solution.

Endpoint Detection

Continue adding the EDTA solution until the indicator changes color. In the case of EBT, the solution will turn from colorless to sky blue (**Color Code - #6F88D0**), indicating that all the calcium carbonate has reacted and the solution is now slightly acidic.

Result

It has been discovered through systematic experimentation that employing 80 ml of deionized water (DM water) instead of the previously recommended 100 ml as the solvent yields superior results. The findings underscore the enduring relevance of traditional analytical methods while showcasing their adaptability in contemporary pharmaceutical manufacturing and quality assurance.

Sample No	Standard Sample Burett Reading (Known)	Tablet Sample Burett Reading (100 ml DM Water)
1	14.5	15.9
2	14.6	15.7
3	14.1	15.9
4	14.9	15.6
5	14.5	16.3

Table: 1

Chart: 1

Sample No	Standard Sample Burette Reading (Known)	Tablet Sample Burette Reading (80 ml DM Water)
1	14.5	14.5
2	14.6	14.6
3	14.1	14.1
4	14.9	14.9
5	14.5	14.5

Table: 2

Chart: 2

Discussion

If we use 100 ml water the equivalence point does not change accurately while if we use 80 ml, it does. The following chart shows the level of accuracy. We can see that the values are fluctuating rapidly while we are using 100 ml DM water as diluents (See Table 1 and Chart 1). However, the values are stable if we use 80 ml DM water to dilute the solution (See Table 2 and Chart 2).

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